

POLIRURAL

SLOVAKIA

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Structure

1. Slovak foresight – constitutional and governance reform
2. Lessons from foresight and recommendations to overcome challenges
3. Main results achieved
4. Vision statement > Doctrene
5. Action Plan developement, evaluations and adoption
6. Monitoring Committee
7. Foresight case study
8. Tools usage

Slovak Foresight : CONSTITUTIONAL & GOVERNANCE REFORM

Legally binding VISION (DOCTRENE) for more attractive rural areas

- a new push for a positive, meaningful and lasting difference
- continuity, stability, clarity and strategic direction
- real needs on the ground

Lessons from foresight and recommendations

1. **Complexity** – proactively showcase uniqueness of foresight and be a role model
2. **Communication** – listen to understand, not to reply and find the right balance
3. **Stakeholders** - involve on a regular, convenient, understandable & continued basis
4. **Gaps** in availability of data and documents
5. **Low respect and trust** in public authorities among stakeholders – be the bridge
6. **Current policies** are not people centered but **money centered**
7. Public authorities still have the tendency to **decide behind the close doors**
8. **We brought some optimism into deeply rooted pessimism**

Main Results

- Multi-stakeholder collaboration

	Meetings/Surveys		PARTICIPANTS	out of it women	out of it men
TOTAL:	20		1704	932	782
- on-line	12		1130	558	582
- off-line		8	574	374	200

- Good cooperation with public authorities

- Gov. Office for CS engagement – joint webinar, events
- Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development – working groups for Strategic Plan, evaluation and new section for strategies, analyses and cross-sectional activities
- Ministry of Investments and Regional Development - working group for Structural Funds
- National Parliament – Rural Day in Sept. 2020 and Oct. 2022

- EU Vision developed simultaneously with similar results

- stronger, connected, resilient, prosperous
- ENRD – dedicated workshop, conference, TG on rural revitalization, Rural Pact

- VISION document + Action Plan and Roadmap + Monitoring Com.

Main Results cont.

- New way of stakeholders consultations tested and promoted with the following guiding principles
- Webpage with all results published www.atraktivnyvidiek.sk
- 8 case studies + Regional panel

Pilot area	Policy		Rural Community		Rural Newcomer		Scientific		TOTAL
	Female	Male	Female	Male	Female	Male	Female	Male	
Slovakia	5	2	14	6	7	5	5	1	45

VISION STATEMENT – living definition

DOCTRENE

On the basis of the “Vision” enshrined in the constitutional law adopted in the National Parliament of Slovakia in 2024 providing strategic orientation reflecting the real needs on the ground and long-term sustainable support through various financial instruments, Slovak rural areas in 2040 are a much better off and thriving with many positive environmental, societal and economic improvements already in place and thus gradually becoming more and more attractive, climate friendly, close to being carbon neutral, lively and vibrant place for living, working, leisure and investment. Full orchestration is guaranteed from different policy areas across the whole public governance structures.

Rural areas are well connected within them and with cities. Internet connection has improved all over the country.

The symbiosis between city and rural areas is safeguarded.

Rural entrepreneurs are the leaders in the region. There are structure supporting them in place. There are new opportunities for employment and new sectors have evolved in the area of services, circular economy and energy. Working from home in terms of networking shared spaces is more common.

Stakeholders and actors were actively, inclusively and transparently supporting its implementation and were consulted at all stages and the flow of information in both directions, from the bottom down and from the down to the top, was timely, constructive, constant and for the common good of rural areas and its people. Governance structures are in place and functioning for facilitation of these discussions. Research, transfer of knowledge and innovation have a new role combined with the new roles of governance and collaboration, as well as constant direct engagement of citizens at all levels.

VISION STATEMENT – living definition

DOCTRENE

The Slovak food system has undergone a paradigm shift towards a more sustainable, environmentally friendly and resilient one. People working in agriculture and food production are thriving and being encouraged to continue with their descent life in this economic area. No pesticides or chemicals are being used for food production. The quality of soil is improving and its degradation was reversed. GMO was abolished completely in the whole EU. Farmers, food producers and extension advisory officers are well trained. Farmers have sufficient inputs they need, market is available and developed in parallel with farmers adopting new practices. Decent prices for farmers are ensured. COVID pandemic provided a unique opportunity to restart the rural areas in a new more progressive, sustainable and resilient way. The whole agricultural production is organic.

People living in rural areas are happy and content. Science, education and transfer of knowledge have gained their respectful place in the rural society and serve as the key tool for innovations and development across all sectors of diversified rural economy. People actively, keenly and voluntarily participate in the decision making processes that relate to them and at all stages because they can see their own impact on the ground. Participatory mechanisms are in place, well-functioning and supported by sufficient personal and financial capacities.

Action Plan development

- Consulted on several occasions with stakeholders
- 5 rounds of consultations (1 online and 4 physical)
over 6 months (October 2021 – June 2022)
involving **396 people** (245 women and 151 men)
- 4th version submitted in April 2022
- 5th version in the process of elaboration
- Ongoing consultations with the MofA&RD on possible adoption
– 2 options under discussion
- Evaluations: Ex Ante (December 2021) – 42 survey responses
Ex Durante (June 2022) – 41 survey responses

Conclusions and recommendations of Evaluations

- Engagement of stakeholders is a new norm, yet to be recognized.
- Structures and consultations mechanisms, incl. financing, need to be introduced.
- The process of development of the „Vision“ and AP can serve as role models for such processes.
- Highlighted in an event by the Office of Government Plenipotentiary for development of civil society engagement.
- Stakeholders need to see that they can directly influence the policies affecting them and the space they live in. The foresight is the perfect model for guaranteeing this.

Action Plan

INSTITUTIONAL and GOVERNANCE issues are on the top of the enabling factors effecting the whole “Vision” implementation:

- Consider agriculture and rural areas as a strategic sector.
- Achieve stability and continuity in support and strategic mission oriented thinking.
- Improve coordination among different ministries and sectors of economy.
- Paradigm shift in how we view and treat rural areas.
- Increase the efficiency of funds use.
- Improve technical and professional capacities.
- Functioning consultation mechanisms.
- Use pandemic as a driver for restart of rural areas.
- Establish permanent foresight activities.
- Settle long lasting land reform.

Conclusions and recommendations of Evaluations – cont.

- From the consultations with the MofA&RD it is clear that there are no personal capacities neither experience in this area and training of civil servants would be highly recommended, as well as creating the personal and financial capacities for conducting regular foresight activities.
- Vision document is the outcome of the Polirural project, but input into further consultation processes that already started during the running of the project, but need to continue on after its ending. This is one of the tasks of the newly established Monitoring Committee.
- Regular Ex-Durante evaluation twice a year would provide a reliable tool to progress with the implementation of Action Plan.

Monitoring Committee

- Established at the closing conference in June 2022.
- First 6 members nominated and membership to be extended to the public authorities.
- Membership is well balanced in terms of gender, age and expertise.
- First meeting planned in October 2022.
- Guarantees a continuation of the activities after the conclusion of the project.
- The whole foresight process and its outcomes will be presented to the parliamentarians in October at the premises of the national parliament.
- Important task is to keep the Committee alive.
- Transparency will be safeguarded through maintaining the webpage created in Slovak.

Foresight case study – already included partially in the VISION

Plans till the end of September:

- Updates, proofreading and edits
- Translation into Slovak
- Publish on the webpage the full version
- Describe the foresight process experience
- Prepare a short version in Slovak
- Prepare an article to be published and disseminated via different platforms.

Tools usage after the project

- Regional SDM: improvements are needed in terms of data
- Semex: improvements are needed in terms of availability of documents and in relevant formats; possible use in other projects
- Rural Attractiveness Explorer: potential
- Digital Innovation Hub: Slovak version under development in cooperation with the Czech provider
- Atlas of Best Practices: 8 Slovak cases are available in Slovak on webpage www.atraktivnyvidiek.sk

